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Rana Abdullayeva
Dc. Sc. (Art Study), Professor
Institute of Architecture and Art of ANAS
(Azerbaijan)

rena-cult@yahoo.com

ILHAM ALIYEV - THE SUCCESSOR OF THE CULTURAL POLICY OF HEYDAR ALIYEV

Abstract. The article discusses various aspects of the cultural policy pursued by the President of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, in 2003–2023. Note that a unique situation has developed in Azerbaijan when two generations of the supreme power consistently pursue a single course of systemic transformation and modernization of all cultural institutions. The continuity of the cultural policy of President I. Aliyev lies in the legislative framework development in the sphere of culture, the full support of cultural and art workers, the field of preserving cultural heritage, and reliance on national cultural values. The decisive role of such conceptual documents as “Azerbaijan 2020: a look into the Future” and “Azerbaijan 2030: National Priorities for socio-economic development”, adopted on the initiative of President I. Aliyev, in the development of modern culture, is emphasized.

Keywords: Ilham Aliyev, Heydar Aliyev, cultural policy, continuity, art.

Introduction. In the field of cultural policy, President I. Aliyev is a consistent successor, the true successor of the nationwide leader Heydar Aliyev, who, in his speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 10th anniversary of the state independence of the Republic of Azerbaijan, noted: “... that in a short historical period a democratic, legal, secular state practically was built and put into operation. Numerous laws adopted during this time made it possible to ensure its vital activity, self-dependence and security, to carry out reforms in all areas of public life and to obtain concrete results.

For the first time in the centuries-old history of our people, Azerbaijan has taken a worthy place in the world, is represented in all authoritative

international organizations, and has established close mutually beneficial cooperation with many states on all continents of the planet” [1].

The interpretation of the main material. The tradition of the priority development of culture and art, the all-round state support of cultural and art workers, founded by Heydar Aliyev, received not only further advancement but also a qualitatively new content during the tenure of İlham Aliyev in the high post of head of the Azerbaijani state. One can say that a unique situation has developed in our country in this area when two generations of the supreme power are consistently pursuing a single course of systemic transformation and modernization of all cultural institutions. At the same time, an inextricable link with the centuries-old traditions of the Azerbaijani people and reliance on the spiritual and aesthetic values of the Azerbaijani nation distinguishes the cultural policy of both the nationwide leader and President I. Aliyev. The direct relay race of the cultural policy of Heydar Aliyev and İlham Aliyev is filled with remarkable harmony, many non-random landmark events and natural coincidences.

Respect for the state symbols of the Republic of Azerbaijan – flag, coat of arms, and anthem – was established during the rule of Heydar Aliyev. Today this attitude to the symbols of statehood has been raised to new heights. Under the decree of President İlham Aliyev, State Flag Day was established on November 9, and National Flag Museum was founded. A unique object of the urban environment has appeared in the capital: a flagpole with a fluttering tricolour flag rises above the museum building, which has no analogues in the world in size.

The modern town-planning structure of Baku started to take shape in the late 1960s and 1970s when nationwide leader Heydar Aliyev became head of the Republic for the first time. At that time, have formed the major architectural ensembles of the capital, grew numerous residential areas, laid gardens and parks, and intensively developed the city’s transport infrastructure. Although Azerbaijan was in an economic crisis when Heydar Aliyev once again headed the country in 1993, the updating process of the appearance of the capital and other cities of Azerbaijan continued. As a result of the conclusion of the oil contract of the century in 1994 and the settling of the economy, a real construction boom arose in Azerbaijan.

After taking the office of President by İlham Aliyev, a qualitatively new stage in the development of architecture and urban planning in Azerbaijan has begun. The image of Baku and many other cities in our country has

transformed unrecognisably. Ultra-modern buildings organically fit into the panorama of the capital, both in appearance and internal equipment, meeting the latest trends in world architectural design. These hotels, exhibitions and office buildings made of glass and metal constructions make unexpected accents to the city's silhouette.

One of the characteristic features of the ultra-new image of the capital is the three flame towers visible from different points of the city and the restoration and reconstruction of residential and public buildings and public spaces in the centre of Baku. With great enthusiasm, Baku residents welcomed the renovation of the very heart of the city – Fountain Square – a favourite place for walks of residents of the capital. Over the past few years, Seaside Boulevard, which received the status of a national park, has been completely transformed; all conditions have been created here for the recreation and entertainment of citizens. This aesthetic waterfront dominance of our city is the favourite and most beautiful leisure place of Baku citizens and guests of the capital.

The decree of President Ilham Aliyev on August 18, 2006, «On the Restoration and Protection of Historical and Architectural Monuments in the Capital of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Baku», has created a radical turning point in this area. Particular attention has been paid to preserving their original appearance.

Fifteen years ago, on April 2, 2007, the President signed a decree on «Monuments of Monumental Sculpture, Memorial and Architectural Complexes in the Republic of Azerbaijan». President Ilham Aliyev initiated the creation of sculpture monuments to a number of artists and cultural figures and personally attended the inauguration of many of them. It refers to the monument erected for great poet Mirza Alakbar Sabir near Shamakhy city, the memorial to singer and composer Muslim Magomayev on his grave in the Alley of Honor, great composer Fikret Amirov on the Baku street of the same name, genius singer Bulbul on the Avenue of the same name. With the President of Austria, Heinz Fischer, President I. Aliyev participated in unveiling the monument to the brilliant composer Mozart and with the President of Serbia – to the great Serbian scientist Nikola Tesla in Baku. Most recently, in honour of the 80th anniversary of the birth of Muslim Magomayev, his monument has been erected on Seaside Boulevard.

By President's I. Aliyev order, the historical and ethnographic complex «The World of Dede Gorgud» was laid in the Narimanov district of Baku,

and a monument to this hero of the national epic was erected. Also, by order of the President, a memorial to the national hero Koroghlu was established in Baku.

Already back in distant 2009, the Museum of Modern Art was opened, becoming a calling card for Azerbaijani avant-garde art and design. The museum has a collection of over 800 works by Azerbaijani artists and sculptors working mainly in the modernist style. The works of masters such as Sattar Bahlulzadeh, Beyukagha Mirzazadeh, Elmira Shakhtakhtinskaya, Tahir Salakhov, Omar Eldarov, and Nadir Abdurakhmanov are exhibited in the museum. The design author of the museum is the well-known artist Altay Sadykhzadeh. President Ilham Aliyev, First Vice-President of Azerbaijan Mehriban Aliyeva, and UNESCO Director-General Koichiro Matsuura attended the opening ceremony.

According to the order of President Ilham Aliyev, issued several years ago, in addition to the Museum of Modern Art, the Museum of Independence and the ship museum «Surakhany» were created in the capital. A new venue for the Carpet and Applied Arts Museum, which celebrated its 55th anniversary last year, was opened.

It is necessary to stress the enormous role of the President of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation, the First Vice-President of the country Mehriban Aliyeva, in the global humanitarian projects implementation of the head of the Republic of Azerbaijan I. Aliyev. In the format of the activities of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation, the musical art of Azerbaijan and its pearl – mugham, as well as the Azerbaijani carpet, both are included in the UNESCO list of intangible heritage, are supported and popularized worldwide.

With the active participation of Mehriban Aliyeva, exhibitions of Azerbaijani art are held on an ongoing basis in many countries of Europe and the world, and a range of cultural projects have been implemented. As a result, an enormous range of people learned and perhaps fell in love with our great cultural heritage, classical and modern music, decorative-applied, and fine arts.

President Ilham Aliyev determined to rearrange the activities of museums following «world standards based on contemporary principles of museum work» and harmonize the expositions «in line with the ideology of Azerbaijanism.»

Over recent years, apart from museum buildings, large-scale reconstruction of concert halls and theatres has been carried out. Thus,

the country's main concert hall, Palace after Heydar Aliyev, has been completely transformed. The buildings of the Azerbaijan State Drama Theatre, Opera and Ballet Theatre, Young Spectator Theatre, and Musical Comedy Theatre have been reconstructed. «Uns» Theater and the Mugham Center, new concert and theatre facilities, were created. I want especially to note the Heydar Aliyev Centre, authored by the world-famous designer Zaha Hadid.

The President's activities in the field of culture are so extensive and multifaceted that in 2008, on the initiative of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of Azerbaijan, a two-volume book entitled «President Ilham Aliyev and Culture» was published. In recent years, Baku has become the centre not only of national culture. Numerous events of both regional and international scale are held in Azerbaijan at the initiative and personal participation of Ilham Aliyev. Among them are the World of Mugham International Festival (2009, 2011, 2012, 2015, 2018), the «Baku Humanitarian Forum: Hopes and Challenges», the International Forum on Intercultural Dialogue, and many others. We have all witnessed the grandiose song festival – Eurovision 2012, held in Baku.

The authority of the President and the country has grown so much that Baku became the capital of Islamic culture in 2009. In his speech at the opening ceremony of the Year of «Baku – Capital of Islamic Culture – 2009», the President of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, said that such cultural initiatives play an important role in bringing Islamic countries together and solving global problems. «I am grateful to ISESCO and the Organization of the Islamic Conference, which played a significant role in making Baku the capital of Islamic culture. It is a very great momentous event for Azerbaijan. I would say it is a pride for Baku [2]. The year 2017 was announced as the year of Islamic solidarity by the presidential decree. It was another very significant event for Azerbaijan.

The role of our President in preserving, strengthening, and promoting Azerbaijani culture is invaluable. Addressing numerous forums and meetings at the highest level, he constantly informs the audience about the history and modern achievements of the culture of Azerbaijan. On his initiative, our cultural heritage is represented practically in all international institutions and has converged firmly into everyday global information space.

The continuous development of the culture of Azerbaijan in the period 2003-2023 is provided not only by direct management of the processes of

development of science, education, art, sports, etc. A whole range of state programs on the general socio-economic and socio-cultural significance determines it.

The decisive role of such conceptual documents as «Azerbaijan 2020: A Look into the Future» and «Azerbaijan 2030: National Priorities in Socio-Economic Development», adopted on the personal initiative of President İlham Aliyev, should be emphasised.

Conclusion. Today, the issue of the continuity of the cultural policy of I. Aliyev is becoming the subject of a particular study. A separate chapter of the monograph of Namig Abbasov, «The Phenomenon of Heydar Aliyev in the Culture of Azerbaijan» (2023), is devoted to this topic. Here is rightly noted that [3, p. 216]

İlham Aliyev, having fulfilled not only his constitutional duty but also the moral testament of nationwide leader Heydar Aliyev, celebrates his political anniversary, the 20th anniversary of being at the helm of state administration. Garabagh is liberated. «Shusha, you are free! Shusha, we are back!» - the President said, addressing the nation. Declaring 2023, the year of Heydar Aliyev, is a new milestone in the national culture development, another step for Azerbaijan into the future.

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Rəna Abdullayeva (Azərbaycan)

İLHAM ƏLİYEV - HEYDƏR ƏLİYEVİN MƏDƏNİYYƏT SİYASƏTİNİN DAVAMÇISI

Məqalədə Azərbaycan Prezidenti İlham Əliyevin 2003-2023-cü illərdə həyata keçirdiyi mədəniyyət siyasətinin müxtəlif aspektlərindən bəhs edilir. Qeyd olunur ki, Azərbaycanda unikal vəziyyət yaranıb ki, ali hakimiyyətin iki nəsli ardıcıl olaraq bütün mədəniyyət institutlarının sistemli transformasiyası və müasirləşdirilməsinin vahid kursunu həyata keçirir. Prezident

İ.Əliyevin mədəniyyət siyasətinin davamlılığı mədəniyyət sahəsində qanunvericilik bazasının inkişaf etdirilməsindən, mədəniyyət və incəsənət işçilərinin hərtərəfli dəstəklənməsindən, mədəni irsin qorunub saxlanması sahəsində, o cümlədən milli mədəni dəyərlərə söykənməsindədir. Prezident İ.Əliyevin təşəbbüsü ilə qəbul edilmiş “Azərbaycan 2020: gələcəyə baxış” və “Azərbaycan 2030: sosial-iqtisadi inkişafın milli prioritetləri” kimi konseptual sənədlərin müasir mədəniyyətin inkişafında həlledici rolu vurğulanır.

Açar sözlər: İlham Əliyev, Heydər Əliyev, mədəniyyət siyasəti, davamlılıq, incəsənət.

Рена Абдуллаева (Азербайджан)

ИЛЬХАМ АЛИЕВ - ПРЕЕМНИК КУЛЬТУРНОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ ГЕЙДАРА АЛИЕВА

В статье рассматриваются различные аспекты культурной политики, проводимой Президентом Азербайджана Ильхамом Алиевым в период 2003-2023 гг. Отмечается, что в Азербайджане сложилась уникальная ситуация, когда два поколения верховной власти последовательно проводят единый курс системного преобразования и модернизации всех институтов культуры. Преемственность культурной политики Президента И.Алиева заключается в развитии законодательной базы в сфере культуры, всемерной поддержке деятелей культуры и искусства, в области сохранения культурного наследия, а также в опоре на национальные культурные ценности. Подчеркивается решающая роль в развитии современной культуры таких концептуальных документов, как «Азербайджан 2020: взгляд в будущее» и «Азербайджан 2030: Национальные приоритеты социально-экономического развития», принятых по инициативе Президента И.Алиева.

Ключевые слова: Ильхам Алиев, Гейдар Алиев, культурная политика, преемственность, искусство.